
*Received: 15th February 2022**Revised: 10th March 2022**Accepted: 20th April 2022*

FUZZY INVENTORY MODEL FOR DETERIORATING ITEMS WITH POWER PATTERN DEMAND WITH SHORTAGES AND BACKLOGGING**SANJU KUMAR* AND RAVISH KUMAR YADAV****ABSTRACT**

In this paper, we derive a fuzzy inventory model for deteriorating items with power demand patterns allowing shortages and partially backlogging. Time-dependent deterioration rate as well as holding cost have been taken. The total cost depends on two variables, one of those is the time at which the inventory level becomes zero, and the second one is the time length of the planning period. Triangular fuzzy number is assigned to the cost parameter and defuzzified by the signed distance method. Finally, numerical examples are presented to illustrate to calculate optimised results.

Keywords: fuzzy inventory, power pattern demand, shortages, Weibull backlogging, deteriorating item.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is important to understand the demand pattern for management of inventories in business, trade and industry. Harris developed the first inventory model to define the Economic Order Quantity in 1915. Wilson gave generalized economic order quantity model. Generally, the nature of goods is deteriorating in many inventory systems. Initially, the study on inventory management including deteriorating items conducted for fashionable items that deteriorated at the end of the storage period. Ghare and Schrader [1] gave a model for an exponentially decaying inventory with constant demand. Naddor [2] in 1966 introduced a special class of time varying demand known by the power demand pattern which considers the demand rate is constant during the inventory cycle and also allows the situation where primarily withdrawn at the beginning of the period or situation where a larger portion of demand occurs at the end of the inventory cycle. Many research articles based on power demand pattern have been published. Goel and Aggarwal [3] introduced an order level inventory system with power demand pattern for deteriorating items. Saxena and Yadav [6] introduced an ordering policy for non-instantaneous decaying items with stock dependent demand and shortages. Hill [4] gave an inventory model for increasing demand followed by level demand. Sicilia et al. [8] provides a deterministic inventory system with power demand pattern for deteriorating items. Yadav et al. [11] developed an inventory model with volume flexibility, random deterioration and increasing demand rate exponentially. Yadav and Yadav [12] introduced a production model in volume flexibility with cubic demand rate. Sicilia et al. [13] provide an inventory model for deteriorating items with shortages and time varying demand i.e. power demand. Keshavarzfar et al. [17] gave a multi-product pricing and inventory model with production rate proportional to power demand rate. Olalekan and Osertin [20] gave a deteriorating inventory policy for items with power demand and variable holding cost considering shortages.

The real business world is full of uncertainties and thereby imprecision in defining the important parameters of the inventory problem. The fuzzy set theory is a most suitable way to deal with uncertainties. The fuzzy set theory was given by L. A. Zadeh [5]. Bartman and Bach [7] gave in inventory control models and methods. Yadav et al. [9] studied the effect of demand boosting policy on optimal inventory policy for imperfect lot size with backorder in fuzzy environment. Mandal and Islam [14] introduced a fuzzy inventory model for power demand pattern with inflation, shortages under partially backlogging condition. Yadav et al. [15] gave a retailer optimal policy under inflation in fuzzy environment with trade credit. Rajeswari et al. [16] introduced an optimization in fuzzy inventory model for linearly deteriorating items, with power demand, partially backlogging and linear holding cost. A joint pricing, supplier selection, and inventory replenishment model using the logit demand function was introduced by Duan and Ventura [18]. Ban [19] provided an inventory model for non-instantaneous deteriorating items with power demand and partially backlogged shortages in fuzzy environment.

The objective of this paper is to determine optimum inventory cost as well as optimum cycle length for an inventory system with power demand and time dependent holding cost in fuzzy environment. Cost components like products cost, deterioration cost, cost of lost sale, backordering cost are fuzzified by taking triangular fuzzy numbers and defuzzification completed by the signed distance method. Findings are verified by numerical examples.

2. ASSUMPTIONS AND NOTATIONS

2.1 Assumptions

- Only single item has been considered in the inventory model.
- Holding cost, deterioration cost are depends on time.
- **Power demand:-** The demand up to time t is assumed to be $dT \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^m$, where d the average demand during the fixed cycle time T , and m ($0 < m < \infty$) is the pattern index of demand. The demand rate at time t is given by $\left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^{m-1}$, which is known by power demand pattern.

i.e demand at any time t , $D(t) = md \left(\frac{t}{T}\right)^{m-1}$, due to the value of m , three case arises

- 1 $0 < m < 1$.
- 2 $m=1$.
- 3 $m>1$

- **Generalised Triangular Fuzzy Number:-** A fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a, b, c)$, where $a < b < c$ and defined on $\mathbb{R}$, is called a triangular fuzzy number if its membership function is

$$\mu_A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x - a}{b - a}, & a \leq x \leq b \\ \frac{c - x}{c - b}, & b \leq x \leq c \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

When $a = b = c$, we have fuzzy point $(c, c, c) = \tilde{c}$. The family of all triangular fuzzy number on $\mathbb{R}$ is denoted as $F_N = \{(a,b,c): a < b < c, \forall a,b,c \in \mathbb{R}\}$.

The α -cut of $\tilde{A} = (a, b, c) \in F_N$, $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$ is $A(\alpha) = [A_L(\alpha), A_R(\alpha)]$,

Where $A_L(\alpha) = a + (b - a)\alpha$ and $A_R(\alpha) = c - (c - b)\alpha$ are the left and right end points of $A(\alpha)$.

Figure 1: Triangular fuzzy number

- **Defuzzification:-** The process of conversion of a fuzzy set into a crisp set is known as defuzzification. There are several methods are available for defuzzification. But in this research work, we have used signed distance method.

The signed distance of $\tilde{A}$ is defined by the given integration

$$d(\tilde{A}, 0) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 [\tilde{A}_L(\alpha) + \tilde{A}_R(\alpha)] d\alpha$$

$$= \frac{a+2b+c}{4}$$

If triangular fuzzy number is the triplet $\tilde{A} = (a, b, c)$ where $b, a = b - \Delta_1$ and $c = b + \Delta_2$ are crisp numbers satisfying the condition $a \leq b \leq c$ then

$$d(\tilde{A}, 0) = \frac{a + 2b + c}{4} = \frac{\Delta_2 - \Delta_1}{4} + b$$

2.1 NOTATIONS

Following notations will be used throughout the paper

A - Ordering cost per cycle.

C – Per unit cost.

θt . - Time dependent Deterioration rate.

$h(t)$ - Holding cost per unit per unit time, $h(t) = a + bt$ where $a > 0$, and $b > 0$.

C_b - Backordering cost per unit short per unit time.

C_l - Cost of lost sale per unit.

C_d - Deterioration cost per unit.

T - Time length of cycle, and $T = (t_1 + t_2)$

t_1 - Time at which the the inventory level becomes zero.

$\tilde{h}(t)$ – Fuzzy holding cost per unit per unit time, $\tilde{h}(t) = \tilde{a} + bt$ where $a > 0$, and $b > 0$.

$\tilde{C}$ – Fuzzy cost per unit.

$\tilde{C}_b$ – Fuzzy backordering cost per unit short per unit time.

$\tilde{C}_l$ – Fuzzy cost of lost sale per unit.

$\tilde{C}_d$ - Fuzzy Deterioration cost per unit.

Q – The ordered quantity during the cycle of length time T , and $Q = (q_1 + q_2)$, where q_1 is maximum inventory level during the time period $[0, T]$, and q_2 is maximum backordered units during stock out period.

B – Backlogging rate, where backordered item follows the backlog function $B(t) = e^{-\alpha t}$, where $B(0) = 1$ and $B(T) \geq 0, 0 < \alpha < 1, t > 1$.

3. MATHEMATICAL MODELS

3.1 Crisp model

Inventory level during the period $[0, t_1]$ controlled by the following differential equation,

$$\frac{d}{dt} I_1(t) + \theta t I_1(t) = -md \left(\frac{t}{T} \right)^{m-1}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{1}$$

With the condition $I_1(t) = 0$ when $t = t_1$. So we have, inventory level at any time t ,

$$I_1(t) = \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \theta t^2 \right) \left(\frac{t_1^m}{m} - \frac{t^m}{m} \right) + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} (t_1^{m+2} - t^{m+2}) \right\}, \quad 0 \leq t \leq t_1 \tag{2}$$

Inventory level during shortage period controlled by the following equation,

$$\frac{d}{dt} I_2(t) = -e^{-\alpha(T-t)} .md \left(\frac{t}{T} \right)^{m-1}, \quad t_1 \leq t \leq T \tag{3}$$

With boundary condition $I_2(t) = 0$ when $t = t_1$, the solution of equation (3), we get

$$I_2(t) = -\frac{md}{T^{m-1}} \left\{ \frac{1}{m} (t^m - t_1^m) - \frac{\alpha T}{m} (t^m - t_1^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (t^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \tag{4}$$

The maximum positive inventory q_1 , obtained by putting $t = 0$ in equation (2),

$$q_1 = I_1(0) = \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} \left\{ \frac{t_1^m}{m} + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} t_1^{m+2} \right\} \tag{5}$$

The maximum backordered unit's q_2 is obtained by using equation (4)

$$q_2 = -I_2(T) = \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} (T^m - t^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \tag{6}$$

Hence the order size Q during the planning period $[0, T]$, from equation (5) and (6), we have

$$Q = q_1 + q_2$$

$$Q = \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} \left[\left\{ \frac{t_1^m}{m} + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} t_1^{m+2} \right\} + \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} (T^m - t^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \right] \tag{7}$$

Since the inventory level during the period $(0, t_1)$ is positive so the holding cost is calculated for the time period $(0, t_1)$ only.

Holding cost

$$HC = \int_0^{t_1} h(t) I_1(t) dt$$

$$HC = \int_0^{t_1} (a + bt) \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \theta t^2 \right) \left(\frac{t_1^m}{m} - \frac{t^m}{m} \right) + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} (t_1^{m+2} - t^{m+2}) \right\} dt$$

$$HC = \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} \left[\frac{at_1^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{a\theta t_1^{m+3}}{3(m+3)} + \frac{bt_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \frac{b\theta t_1^{m+4}}{8(m+4)} \right] \tag{8}$$

Backordering cost

$$BC = C_b \int_{t_1}^T -I_2(t) dt$$

$$BC = \frac{C_b md}{T^{m-1}} \left[\frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m(m+1)} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) - \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} t_1 (T - t_1) + \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)(m+2)} (T^{m+2} - t_1^{m+2}) - \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)} t_1^{m+1} (T - t_1) \right] \tag{9}$$

Cost of lost sale

$$LS = C_i \int_{t_1}^T (1 - e^{-\alpha(T-t)}) \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} t^{m-1} dt$$

$$LS = \frac{C_i \alpha md}{T^{m-1}} \left[\frac{T^{m+1}}{m(m+1)} - t_1^m \left(\frac{T}{m} - \frac{t_1}{m+1} \right) \right] \tag{10}$$

Deterioration cost

$$DC = C_d \left[Q - \int_0^{t_1} \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} t^{m-1} dt - \int_{t_1}^T e^{-\alpha(T-t)} \cdot \frac{md}{T^{m-1}} t^{m-1} dt \right]$$

$$DC = \frac{C_d md}{T^{m-1}} \frac{\theta t_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} \tag{11}$$

Purchase cost

$$PC = C \times Q$$

$$PC = \frac{Cmd}{T^{m-1}} \left[\left\{ \frac{t_1^m}{m} + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} t_1^{m+2} \right\} + \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} (T^m - t^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \right] \quad (12)$$

Hence, the average total cost per unit time given by,

$$K(T, t_1) = \frac{1}{T} [OC + HC + BC + LS + DC + PC]$$

$$K(T, t_1) = \frac{md}{T^m} \left[\begin{aligned} & A + \frac{at_1^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{a\theta t_1^{m+3}}{3(m+3)} + \frac{bt_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \frac{b\theta t_1^{m+4}}{8(m+4)} \\ & + C_b \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m(m+1)} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) - \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} t_1 (T - t_1) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)(m+2)} (T^{m+2} - t_1^{m+2}) - \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)} t_1^{m+1} (T - t_1) \right\} \\ & + C_l \alpha \left\{ \frac{T^{m+1}}{m(m+1)} - t_1^m \left(\frac{T}{m} - \frac{t_1}{m+1} \right) \right\} + \frac{C_d \theta t_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \\ & C \left\{ \frac{t_1^m}{m} + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} t_1^{m+2} + \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} (T^m - t^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \right] \quad (13)$$

3.2 FUZZY MODEL

In the real world, any kind of cost could not be precise. So we are dealing with impreciseness by assigning triangular fuzzy numbers to the different cost parameters C, C_b, C_d, C_l and a such that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C} &= (C - \delta_1, C, C + \delta_2) \text{ where } \delta_1, \delta_2 > 0 \text{ and } C > \delta_1 > 0 \\ \tilde{C}_b &= (C_b - \delta_3, C_b, C_b + \delta_4) \text{ where } \delta_3, \delta_4 > 0 \text{ and } C_b > \delta_3 > 0 \\ \tilde{C}_d &= (C_d - \delta_5, C_d, C_d + \delta_6) \text{ where } \delta_5, \delta_6 > 0 \text{ and } C_d > \delta_5 > 0 \\ \tilde{C}_l &= (C_l - \delta_7, C_l, C_l + \delta_8) \text{ where } \delta_7, \delta_8 > 0 \text{ and } C_l > \delta_7 > 0 \\ \tilde{a} &= (a - \delta_9, a, a + \delta_{10}) \text{ where } \delta_9, \delta_{10} > 0 \text{ and } a > \delta_9 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

Total average cost of the inventory per unit time in fuzzy sense is given by

$$K(T, t_1) = \frac{md}{T^m} \left[\begin{aligned} & A + a \left(\frac{t_1^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{\theta t_1^{m+3}}{3(m+3)} \right) + \frac{bt_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \frac{b\theta t_1^{m+4}}{8(m+4)} \\ & + C_b \left\{ \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m(m+1)} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) - \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} t_1 (T - t_1) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)(m+2)} (T^{m+2} - t_1^{m+2}) - \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)} t_1^{m+1} (T - t_1) \right\} \\ & + C_l \alpha \left\{ \frac{T^{m+1}}{m(m+1)} - t_1^m \left(\frac{T}{m} - \frac{t_1}{m+1} \right) \right\} + \frac{C_d \theta t_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \\ & C \left\{ \frac{t_1^m}{m} + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} t_1^{m+2} + \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} (T^m - t^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \right] \quad (14)$$

Now we defuzzify (10) by applying signed distance method, we have

$$d(K, 0) = \frac{md}{T^m} \left[\begin{aligned} & A + d(a, 0) \left(\frac{t_1^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{\theta t_1^{m+3}}{3(m+3)} \right) + \frac{bt_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \frac{b\theta t_1^{m+4}}{8(m+4)} \\ & + d(C_b, 0) \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m(m+1)} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) - \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} t_1 (T - t_1) \\ & + \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)(m+2)} (T^{m+2} - t_1^{m+2}) - \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)} t_1^{m+1} (T - t_1) \end{aligned} \right\} \\ & + d(C_l, 0) \alpha \left\{ \frac{T^{m+1}}{m(m+1)} - t_1^m \left(\frac{T}{m} - \frac{t_1}{m+1} \right) \right\} + \frac{d(\overline{C_d}, 0) \theta t_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \\ & d(\overline{C}, 0) \left\{ \frac{t_1^m}{m} + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} t_1^{m+2} + \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} (T^m - t_1^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \right] \quad (15)$$

Where

$$d(C, 0) = \frac{\delta_2 - \delta_1}{4} + C, \quad \text{and} \quad d(C_b, 0) = \frac{\delta_4 - \delta_3}{4} + C_b$$

$$d(C_d, 0) = \frac{\delta_6 - \delta_5}{4} + C_d, \quad \text{and} \quad d(C_l, 0) = \frac{\delta_8 - \delta_7}{4} + C_l$$

$$d(a, 0) = \frac{\delta_{10} - \delta_9}{4} + a$$

Let $d(K, 0) \cong K(T, t_1)$

Hence,

$$K(T, t_1) = \frac{md}{T^m} \left[\begin{aligned} & A + \left(\frac{\delta_{10} - \delta_9}{4} + a \right) \left(\frac{t_1^{m+1}}{m+1} + \frac{\theta t_1^{m+3}}{3(m+3)} \right) + \frac{bt_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} + \frac{b\theta t_1^{m+4}}{8(m+4)} \\ & + \left(\frac{\delta_4 - \delta_3}{4} + C_b \right) \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m(m+1)} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) - \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} t_1 (T - t_1) \\ & + \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)(m+2)} (T^{m+2} - t_1^{m+2}) - \frac{\alpha}{(m+1)} t_1^{m+1} (T - t_1) \end{aligned} \right\} \\ & + \left(\frac{\delta_8 - \delta_7}{4} + C_l \right) \alpha \left\{ \frac{T^{m+1}}{m(m+1)} - t_1^m \left(\frac{T}{m} - \frac{t_1}{m+1} \right) \right\} + \left(\frac{\delta_6 - \delta_5}{4} + C_d \right) \frac{\theta t_1^{m+2}}{2(m+2)} \\ & + \left(\frac{\delta_2 - \delta_1}{4} + C \right) \left\{ \frac{t_1^m}{m} + \frac{\theta}{2(m+2)} t_1^{m+2} + \frac{(1-\alpha T)}{m} (T^m - t_1^m) + \frac{\alpha}{m+1} (T^{m+1} - t_1^{m+1}) \right\} \end{aligned} \right] \quad (16)$$

4 ALGORITHM

To optimize total average cost per unit time, the value of T and t_1 can be obtained by solving the following equations for both crisp and fuzzy model.

$$\frac{\partial K(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial K(T, t_1)}{\partial T} = 0$$

Provided that the following conditions must be satisfied,

$$\frac{\partial^2 K(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1^2} > 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 K(T, t_1)}{\partial T^2} > 0$$

and

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 K(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1^2}\right)\left(\frac{\partial^2 K(T, t_1)}{\partial T^2}\right) - \left(\frac{\partial^2 K(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1 \partial T}\right)^2 > 0$$

5. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

5.1 Crisp Model

$d = 100$ units / week, $A = \$40$ per order, $a = 0.3$, $b = 0.05$, $C = \$8$ per unit, $C_b = \$12$ / unit / week, $C_i = \$15$ / unit, $C_d = \$10$ / unit, $\alpha = 0.7$, $\theta = 0.05$, $m = 1$

The solution of crisp model is

$t_1^* = 2.4967$ weeks, $T^* = 3.7334$ weeks, $K^*(T, t_1) = \$1700.7$

And

$$\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1^2} = 206.4273 > 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial T^2} = 103.5606 > 0$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1^2}\right)\left(\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial T^2}\right) - \left(\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1 \partial T}\right)^2 = 20187.7541217 > 0$$

Figure 1:

5.2 FUZZY MODEL

$d = 100$ units / week, $A = \$40$ per order, $a = 0.5$, $b = 0.05$, $C = \$8$ per unit, $C_b = \$12$ / unit / week, $C_i = \$15$ / unit, $C_d = \$10$ / unit, $\alpha = 0.7$, $\theta = 0.05$, $m = 1$, $\delta_1 = 3$, $\delta_2 = 1$, $\delta_3 = 5$, $\delta_4 = 2$, $\delta_5 = 4$, $\delta_6 = 2$, $\delta_7 = 5$, $\delta_8 = 3$, $\delta_9 = 0.04$, $\delta_{10} = 0.02$,

The solution of fuzzy model

$t_1^* = 2..5600$ weeks, $T^* = 3.8213$ weeks, $K^*(T, t_1) = \$1639.7$

And

$$\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1^2} = 118.2408 > 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial T^2} = 18.6521 > 0$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1^2}\right)\left(\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial T^2}\right) - \left(\frac{\partial^2 K^*(T, t_1)}{\partial t_1 \partial T}\right)^2 = 1.50292047 > 0$$

Figure 2:

6. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

In this section we study the effects of change in parameters θ , A , α , and d . Three values are considered for the index of the power demand pattern m , that is $m = 0.5, 1$ and 1.5 .

6.1 Crisp Model

We choose the values for the deterioration fraction $\theta = 0.01, 0.03, 0.05$, and 0.08 . Computed results are reported in table 1. These results indicate that optimal cost K increases as the deterioration fraction increases, but optimal cost decreases as index of power demand pattern m increases. The minimum cost per unit time is attained when $\theta = 0.01$ and $m = 1.5$.

Table. 1

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, \theta = 0.05, A = 40, a = 0.5, b = 0.05, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week}, C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \alpha = 0.5,$

Deterioration	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$\theta = 0.01$	$t_1 = 1.5921, T = 2.7095$ $K(t_1, T) = 2116.8$	$t_1 = 3.2177, T = 4.6586$ $K(t_1, T) = 1534.2$	$t_1 = 2.1908, T = 3.7669$ $K(t_1, T) = 1274.5$
$\theta = 0.03$	$t_1 = 1.6552, T = 2.6699$ $K(t_1, T) = 2124.3$	$t_1 = 2.9101, T = 4.3753$ $K(t_1, T) = 1635.7$	$t_1 = 2.1436, T = 3.7573$ $K(t_1, T) = 1304.7$
$\theta = 0.05$	$t_1 = 1.8166, T = 2.6313$ $K(t_1, T) = 2133.5$	$t_1 = 2.6929, T = 4.1792$ $K(t_1, T) = 1712.2$	$t_1 = 2.0985, T = 3.7475$ $K(t_1, T) = 1332.8$
$\theta = 0.08$	$t_1 = 1.7514, T = 2.6354$ $K(t_1, T) = 2146.9$	$t_1 = 2.4562, T = 3.9701$ $K(t_1, T) = 1800.3$	$t_1 = 2.0348, T = 3.7328$ $K(t_1, T) = 1371.6$

In table 2, we analyse the optimal policy when the ordering cost A and the power demand pattern index m vary at different values. The optimal cost is obtained at $m = 1.5$ and $A = 20$. Results of this table indicate that inventory cost decreases as ordering cost decreases and the inventory cost decreases when m increases.

Table 2

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, \theta = 0.05, a = 0.5, b = 0.05, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week}, C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \alpha = 0.5,$

Ordering Cost	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$A = 20$	$t_1 = 1.6589, T = 2.3252$ $K(t_1, T) = 1498.9$	$t_1 = 2.1966, T = 3.5134$ $K(t_1, T) = 1352.3$	$t_1 = 1.9124, T = 3.1605$ $K(t_1, T) = 1204.5$
$A = 30$	$t_1 = 1.7194, T = 2.4928$ $K(t_1, T) = 1820.9$	$t_1 = 2.4343, T = 3.8515$ $K(t_1, T) = 1546.1$	$t_1 = 2.0126, T = 3.4884$ $K(t_1, T) = 1278.7$
$A = 50$	$t_1 = 2.0386, T = 2.7434$ $K(t_1, T) = 2439.5$	$t_1 = 2.9504, T = 4.4892$ $K(t_1, T) = 1861.7$	$t_1 = 2.1764, T = 3.9655$ $K(t_1, T) = 1374.2$
$A = 60$	$t_1 = 2.0430, T = 2.8390$ $K(t_1, T) = 2738.7$	$t_1 = 3.1984, T = 4.7795$ $K(t_1, T) = 2000.5$	$t_1 = 2.2480, T = 4.1556$ $K(t_1, T) = 1407.0$

The sensitivity of the inventory policy with respect to the backlogging parameter is shown in table 3. The best result is obtained at $m = 0.5$ and $\alpha = 0.1$. For $m = 0.5$ cost increases as the value of backlogging parameter increases but cost decreases as backlogging parameter increases for m greater or equal to one.

Table 3

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, A = \$40 \text{ per order}, a = 0.5, b = 0.05, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week},$ $C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \theta = 0.05,$			
Backlogging Parameter	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$\alpha = 0.1$	$t_1 = 4.2425, T = 6.5075$ $K(t_1, T) = 1143.3$	$t_1 = 4.4349, T = 5.8485$ $K(t_1, T) = 1927.7$	$t_1 = 4.2130, T = 4.9026$ $K(t_1, T) = 1951.9$
$\alpha = 0.3$	$t_1 = 2.4205, T = 3.2662$ $K(t_1, T) = 1970.2$	$t_1 = 3.3209, T = 5.3104$ $K(t_1, T) = 1724.0$	$t_1 = 2.7543, T = 4.4378$ $K(t_1, T) = 1478.4$
$\alpha = 0.7$	$t_1 = 1.9501, T = 2.3754$ $K(t_1, T) = 2215.6$	$t_1 = 2.4967, T = 3.7334$ $K(t_1, T) = 1700.7$	$t_1 = 1.8376, T = 3.3710$ $K(t_1, T) = 1244.5$
$\alpha = 0.9$	$t_1 = 1.8438, T = 2.2060$ $K(t_1, T) = 2265.4$	$t_1 = 2.3695, T = 3.4565$ $K(t_1, T) = 1693.5$	$t_1 = 1.6932, T = 3.1211$ $K(t_1, T) = 1186.9$

Now, we have observed variation of optimal cost with respect to the holding cost, for this purpose changes in the value of b is considered in table 4. The minimum cost is obtained when $b = 0.03$ and $m = 1.5$. The inventory cost increases as the value of b increases and cost of inventory decreases as m increases.

Table 4

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, A = \$40 \text{ per order}, a = 0.5, \alpha = 0.5, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week},$ $C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \theta = 0.05,$			
Holding Cost Parameter	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$b = 0.01$	$t_1 = 1.8234, T = 2.6307$ $K(t_1, T) = 2132.4$	$t_1 = 2.7153, T = 4.1992$ $K(t_1, T) = 1704.3$	$t_1 = 2.1034, T = 3.7486$ $K(t_1, T) = 1329.8$
$b = 0.03$	$t_1 = 1.8200, T = 2.6310$ $K(t_1, T) = 2132.9$	$t_1 = 2.7040, T = 4.1891$ $K(t_1, T) = 1708.2$	$t_1 = 2.1009, T = 3.7481$ $K(t_1, T) = 1331.3$
$b = 0.05$	$t_1 = 1.8166, T = 2.6313$ $K(t_1, T) = 2133.5$	$t_1 = 2.6929, T = 4.1792$ $K(t_1, T) = 1712.2$	$t_1 = 2.0985, T = 3.7475$ $K(t_1, T) = 1332.8$
$b = 0.08$	$t_1 = 1.8119, T = 2.6317$ $K(t_1, T) = 2134.3$	$t_1 = 2.6766, T = 4.1646$ $K(t_1, T) = 1718.0$	$t_1 = 2.0948, T = 3.7467$ $K(t_1, T) = 1335.1$

6.2 FUZZY MODEL

Here we observe the variation of $\theta, A, \alpha,$ and d . As above three values are considered for the index of the power demand pattern m , that is $m = 0.5, 1$ and 1.5 .

In table 5 results indicate that fuzzy optimal cost increases as the deterioration fraction increases, but optimal cost decreases as index of power demand pattern m increases. The minimum cost per unit time is attained when $\theta = 0.01$ and $m = 1.5$.

Table 5

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, A = 40, a = 0.5, b = 0.05, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week},$ $C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \alpha = 0.5, \delta_1 = 3, \delta_2 = 1, \delta_3 = 5, \delta_4 = 2, \delta_5 = 4, \delta_6 = 2,$ $\delta_7 = 5, \delta_8 = 3, \delta_9 = 0.04, \delta_{10} = 0.02,$			
Deterioration	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$\theta = 0.01$	$t_1 = 1.6065, T = 2.7364$	$t_1 = 3.3013, T = 4.7673$	$t_1 = 2.2242, T = 3.8339$
$\theta = 0.03$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2064.4$ $t_1 = 1.6667, T = 2.6986$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1475.4$ $t_1 = 2.9784, T = 4.4701$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1211.5$ $t_1 = 2.1761, T = 3.8243$
$\theta = 0.05$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2071.6$ $t_1 = 2.1460, T = 2.6887$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1575.9$ $t_1 = 2.7521, T = 4.2659$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1240.8$ $t_1 = 2.1303, T = 3.8146$
$\theta = 0.08$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2081.1$ $t_1 = 1.7979, T = 2.6608$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2094$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1651.2$ $t_1 = 2.5067, T = 4.0494$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1737.7$	$\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1268.1$ $t_1 = 2.0656, T = 3.7999$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1309.6$

The analysis of the fuzzy optimal policy is discussed in table 6 when the ordering cost A and the power demand pattern index m vary at different values. The fuzzy optimal cost is obtained at $m = 1.5$ and $A = 20$. Results of this table indicate that inventory cost decreases as ordering cost decreases and the inventory cost decreases when m increases.

Table 6

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, \theta = 0.05, a = 0.5, b = 0.05, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week},$ $C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \alpha = 0.5, \delta_1 = 3, \delta_2 = 1, \delta_3 = 5, \delta_4 = 2, \delta_5 = 4, \delta_6 = 2,$ $\delta_7 = 5, \delta_8 = 3, \delta_9 = 0.04, \delta_{10} = 0.02,$			
Ordering Cost	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$A = 20$	$t_1 = 1.6805, T = 2.3450$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1448.8$	$t_1 = 2.3450, T = 3.5808$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1297.4$	$t_1 = 1.9417, T = 3.2157$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1144.5$
$A = 30$	$t_1 = 1.7545, T = 2.5159$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1448.8$	$t_1 = 2.4852, T = 3.9291$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1517.3$	$t_1 = 2.0434, T = 3.5503$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1216.1$
$A = 50$	$t_1 = 2.0036, T = 2.7704$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2384.2$	$t_1 = 3.0165, T = 4.5835$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1798.6$	$t_1 = 2.2091, T = 4.0369$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1307.9$
$A = 60$	$t_1 = 2.0376, T = 2.8720$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2681.8$	$t_1 = 3.2703, T = 4.8803$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1935.6$	$t_1 = 2.2815, T = 4.2307$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1339.3$

The sensitivity of the fuzzy inventory policy with respect to the backlogging parameter is shown in table 7. The best result is obtained at $m = 0.5$ and $\alpha = 0.1$. For $m = 0.5$ cost increases as the value of backlogging parameter increases but cost decreases as backlogging parameter increases for m greater or equal to one

Table 7

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, A = 40, \theta = 0.05, a = 0.5, b = 0.05, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week},$ $C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \delta_1 = 3, \delta_2 = 1, \delta_3 = 5, \delta_4 = 2, \delta_5 = 4, \delta_6 = 2,$ $\delta_7 = 5, \delta_8 = 3, \delta_9 = 0.04, \delta_{10} = 0.02,$			
Backlogging Parameter	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$\alpha = 0.1$	$t_1 = 4.2507, T = 6.5284$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1126.6$	$t_1 = 4.4921, T = 5.9674$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1858.0$	$t_1 = 4.2648, T = 5.0313$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1873.4$
$\alpha = 0.3$	$t_1 = 2.4490, T = 3.2996$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1919.3$	$t_1 = 3.3543, T = 5.3783$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1663.8$	$t_1 = 2.7829, T = 4.5116$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1409.1$
$\alpha = 0.7$	$t_1 = 1.9418, T = 2.3946$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2160.6$	$t_1 = 2.5600, T = 3.8213$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1639.7$	$t_1 = 1.8676, T = 3.4334$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1183.3$
$\alpha = 0.9$	$t_1 = 1.8422, T = 2.2248$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2210.3$	$t_1 = 2.4321, T = 3.5423$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1632.4$	$t_1 = 1.7213, T = 3.1800$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1128.2$

Finally, we have observed variation of fuzzy optimal cost with respect to the holding cost, for this purpose changes in the value of b is considered in table 8. The minimum cost is obtained when $b = 0.01$ and $m = 1.5$. The inventory cost increases as the value of b increases and cost of inventory decreases as m increases.

Table 8

$d = 100 \text{ units / week}, A = 40, \theta = 0.05, a = 0.5, C = \$8 \text{ per unit}, C_b = \$12 / \text{unit / week},$ $C_l = \$15 / \text{unit}, C_d = \$10 / \text{unit}, \alpha = 0.5, \delta_1 = 3, \delta_2 = 1, \delta_3 = 5, \delta_4 = 2, \delta_5 = 4, \delta_6 = 2,$ $\delta_7 = 5, \delta_8 = 3, \delta_9 = 0.04, \delta_{10} = 0.02,$			
Holding Cost Parameter	$m = 0.5$	$m = 1$	$m = 1.5$
$b = 0.01$	$t_1 = 2.824, T = 2.6756$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2079.5$	$t_1 = 2.7767, T = 4.2879$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1643.0$	$t_1 = 2.1356, T = 3.8157$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1265.0$
$b = 0.03$	$t_1 = 2.1173, T = 2.6825$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2080.3$	$t_1 = 2.7643, T = 4.2768$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1647.1$	$t_1 = 2.1329, T = 3.8152$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1266.6$
$b = 0.05$	$t_1 = 2.1460, T = 2.6887$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2081.7$	$t_1 = 2.7521, T = 4.2659$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1651.2$	$t_1 = 2.1303, T = 3.8146$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1268.1$
$b = 0.08$	$t_1 = 2.1824, T = 2.6973$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 2082.4$	$t_1 = 2.7343, T = 4.2499$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1657.3$	$t_1 = 2.1264, T = 3.8137$ $\tilde{K}(t_1, T) = 1270.5$

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an inventory model has been developed to determine the optimal inventory cycle, backordering point, optimal inventory cycle and the average total cost per unit time for deteriorating items. The above-proposed model is fuzzified by a triangular fuzzy number to improve results. Defuzzification has been done by the signed distance method. The demand depends on time and follows a power pattern. Convexity of the average total cost function is also proved. The applicability of the proposed models is demonstrated by examples. Sensitivity analysis was also carried out concerning different parameters and different power pattern indexes.

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